

Studies of kinetics and isotherm effect on Brilliant Green dye with activated carbon

Amita Jaiswal and M. C. Chattopadhyaya*

Environmental Chemistry Research Lab, Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad,
Allahabad-211 002, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : amita_ecsl@rediffmail.com, mcc46@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 11 May 2009, revised 16 July 2009, accepted 21 July 2009

Abstract : Activated carbon prepared from low cost coconut fiber has been utilized as the adsorbent for the removal of basic dyes from aqueous solution. A basic dye, Brilliant Green has been used as the adsorbate. Experiments were conducted at different initial concentration, different adsorbent dose, temperature, pH and different contact time. The most effective removal of color was at pH 7 and the percentage removal increased with the increase in carbon dose, while the percentage removal decreased with increasing initial dye concentration. The adsorption data best fitted with Langmuir than Freundlich isotherm. Kinetic study was also undertaken and it was found that the interaction follows the pseudo-second order than pseudo-first order. Thermodynamic parameters were also calculated.

Keywords : Adsorption, Brilliant Green dye, activated carbon, Freundlich isotherm, Langmuir isotherm.

Introduction

Water pollution is now emerging as a major problem in the developing world and its abatement has always been an issue in our environmental concern today. The wastewater discharged from dyeing processes exhibit high BOD and COD and are highly coloured, hot, alkaline and contains high amounts of solids¹. The disposal of coloured wastes such as dyes and pigments into receiving waters damages the environment, as they are carcinogenic and toxic to humans and aquatic life^{2,3}. Moreover the basic dyes are widely used in several industrial products and effluents of these industries are discharged into natural streams^{4,5}. They also consumed a large quantity of water^{6,7}.

Adsorption has received considerable attention for colour removal from wastewaters as it offers the most economical and effective treatment method. Low cost adsorbents like fly-ash, coal, peat, sawdust⁸, lignite and wood have received considerable interest because of their local availability and low cost⁵. Use of adsorbent like rice husk⁹, coconut coir, banana pith¹⁰, wheat straw, baggase, saw dust^{8,9,11}, used tea leaves, cow dung¹² have been found to be highly effective, cheap and eco-friendly.

In this study, coconut fiber has been chosen as acti-

vated carbon. By using this agricultural waste, it is possible to reduce solid waste disposal problem and also minimize the cost of activated carbon production. The use of coconut fiber for removing pollutants will benefit the environment. Contaminated streams and rivers will be cleaned. This study will provide useful information about the efficiency of activated carbon prepared from coconut fiber in the adsorption of dyes from industrial wastewater.

In the present study Brilliant Green dye was used, which is a cationic dye (Fig. 1). It is also known as emerald green or malachite green G. It is a triphenylmethane dye of the malachite-green series. It is used to dye silk and wool. It occurs as small, shiny, golden crystals soluble in water or alcohol.

Fig. 1. Brilliant Green dye.

Results and discussion

Effect of initial dye concentration and time : The effect of initial concentration of dye solution on the amount of dye adsorbed on the activated carbon was studied with a fixed dose of adsorbent and varying time and initial concentration of dye (Table 1), which reveals that the percentage removal of dye decreases with the increase in initial concentration of dye and increases with increasing time. This might be due to the lack of available active sites on the adsorbent surface compared to the relatively large number of active sites required for the high initial concentration of dye.

Table 1. Effect of initial dye concentration and time on BG removal (in %)

Time (min)	Concn. (ppm)					
	50	100	150	200	250	300
15	71.5	66.0	61.0	55.0	43.0	31.8
30	80.0	77.9	67.5	60.0	49.0	36.5
45	89.5	82.9	73.0	65.0	54.7	39.2
60	92.3	85.5	79.0	68.0	57.2	42.6
90	94.0	87.0	80.0	69.5	59.2	44.5
120	96.0	90.0	85.0	72.0	61.5	46.3

So, activated carbon could remove a maximum 90% of Brilliant Green dye at initial dye concentration of 100 ppm, while for dye concentration of 50 ppm, the adsorption of the dye was well above 96% in 2 h. All cases were studied at neutral pH, temperature 25 °C and adsorbent dose of 0.4 g/100 mL.

Effect of adsorbent dose and time : The effect of varying the activated carbon mass on aqueous dye solution are presented in Table 2.

Data show an increasing percentage removal in dye concentration at a faster rate as the adsorbent mass is increased. An equilibrium percentage removal rate of

Table 2. Effect of adsorbent dose and time on BG removal (in %)

Time (min)	Dose (g)					
	0.1	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.8	1.0
15	35.0	54.0	66.0	77.0	87.0	95.0
30	45.2	62.0	77.9	84.0	93.0	97.0
45	50.0	70.0	82.9	88.3	94.78	98.0
60	54.0	75.0	85.5	91.0	94.0	98.0
90	58.0	79.0	87.0	93.0	98.0	99.5
120	60.0	80.0	90.0	95.3	98.2	99.6

77.9% was achieved with 0.4 g/100 mL in 30 min by activated carbon of adsorbate concentration of 100 ppm. The initial rise in adsorption with adsorbent dose is probably due to bigger driving force and lesser surface area. Larger surface area of the adsorbent and the smaller size of adsorbate favour adsorption. The rate of adsorption is higher in the beginning as sites are available and unimolecular layer increases. Adsorption and desorption occur together and rate become equal at a stage called adsorption equilibrium, when isotherms are applied. With rise in adsorbent dose, there is less commensurate increase in adsorption, resulting from lower adsorptive capacity utilization of adsorbent¹³.

Effect of temperature : Temperature dependence of adsorption process is a complex phenomenon. Thermodynamic parameters, like heat of adsorption and energy of activation play an important role in predicting the adsorption behaviour and both are strongly dependent on temperature. Temperature rise effects the solubility and chemical potential of the adsorbate, the latter being a controlling factor for adsorption.

It has been reported that if solubility of the adsorbate increases with increase in temperature, then chemical potential decreases and both of these effects work in the same direction, causing a decrease in adsorption¹⁴.

On the other hand if temperature has reverse effect on the solubility then both the said effects will act in the opposite direction and adsorption may increase or decrease depending upon the predominant factor.

In the present experiments the adsorption rate at three different temperatures (30, 40 and 50 °C) have been analyzed and presented in Table 3. From the table it is clear that rate of dye uptake increases rapidly from 72.0 to 78.0% with rising temperature from 30 to 50 °C with 0.4 g/100 mL dose in 30 min from 100 ppm dye solution, since the adsorption rate increases as the diffusion coefficient rises with temperature⁴.

Table 3. Effect of temperature and time on BG removal by activated carbon (in %)

Time (min)	Temp. (°C)		
	30	40	50
15	65	66	72
30	72	76	78
45	75	79	83
60	79	84	90
90	81	86	94
120	82	89	96

Effect of pH : With increasing pH of the solution percentage removal of the dye also increases as shown in Table 4. This study was carried out with dye solution of 100 ppm in the pH range of 3.0 to 7.0. The rapid uptake of dye at higher pH indicates that the process could be ion exchange in nature where the positive dye molecules bind with negatively charged adsorbent. Lower pH is unfavourable for adsorption. This is due to hydrogen ion and binding of dye molecule on sorption site.

Table 4. Effect of pH on BG removal by activated carbon (in %)

Time (min)	pH				
	3.0	4.0	5.0	6.0	7.0
15	50.20	54.93	59.64	64.35	66.0
30	52.50	56.12	60.00	75.00	77.9
45	53.46	57.89	61.50	76.54	82.9
60	54.90	58.00	65.90	77.87	85.5
90	59.89	60.00	75.00	78.90	87.0
120	57.00	62.00	75.98	89.90	90.0

Adsorption isotherm : It is important to evaluate the most appropriate correlations for equilibrium curves and to optimize the design of a sorption system. Langmuir and Freundlich isotherm models (Figs. 2 and 3) were used to describe the adsorption equilibrium. Experiments

Fig. 2. Langmuir isotherm model related to dye on activated carbon.

Fig. 3. Freundlich isotherm model related to dye on activated carbon.

tal isotherm data were conducted at an equilibrium time of 120 min for different dosages of adsorbate.

The Langmuir adsorption isotherm is based on the assumption that all sites possess equal affinity for the adsorbate. It may be represented in the linear form as follows¹⁵,

$$C_e/q_e = 1/K_L Q_m + C_e/Q_m \tag{1}$$

where, Q_m is the maximum dye uptake, mg/g, K_L the Langmuir adsorption constant, L/mg. The empirical Freundlich isotherm is based on the equilibrium relationship between heterogeneous surfaces. This isotherm is derived from the assumption that the adsorption sites are distributed exponentially with respect to the heat of adsorption. The logarithmic linear form of Freundlich isotherm may be represented as follows¹⁶,

$$\log q_e/m = \log K_f + 1/n \log C_e \tag{2}$$

where, C_e = equilibrium concentration (mg/L), q_e = amount of dye adsorbed (mg/g), m = adsorbent dose (g). K_f and n = constants.

Adsorption kinetic study : Kinetic models have been used to investigate the mechanism of sorption and potential rate controlling steps, which is helpful for selecting optimum operating conditions for the full-scale batch process¹⁷. Pseudo-first order and pseudo-second order kinetic models were used.

Pseudo-first order model : The pseudo-first order rate expression based on solid capacity is generally expressed as follows¹⁸,

$$dq/dt = k_1 (q_e - q) \tag{3}$$

where, q_e is the amount of dye adsorbed at equilibrium (mg/g), q is the amount adsorbed at time t (mg/g), k_1 is the rate constant of first order adsorption (L/min). After integration and applying boundary conditions, $t = 0$ to t and $q = 0$ to q_e , the integrated form of eq. (3) becomes :

$$\log (q_e - q) = \log q_e - k_1 t/2.303 \tag{4}$$

Values of adsorption rate constant (k_1) for dye adsorption onto activated carbon was determined from the straight line plot of $\log (q_e - q)$ against t . The data were fitted with a poor correlation coefficient (Table 5), indicating that the rate of removal of dye onto activated carbon does not follow the pseudo-first order model.

Pseudo-second order model : The pseudo-second order equation is also based on the sorption capacity of the solid phase. It predicts the behavior over the whole range

Table 5. Parameters and correlation coefficient for the isotherms and kinetics

Freundlich isotherm	K_f	4.736
	$1/n$	0.246
	R^2	0.988
Langmuir isotherm	K_L	3.000
	Q_m	9.090
	R^2	0.992
Pseudo-first order kinetics	k_1	0.026
	R^2	0.958
Pseudo-second order kinetics	k_2	19.184
	R^2	0.999

of data. Furthermore, it is in agreement with chemisorption being the rate controlling step and is expressed as¹⁸,

$$d_q/d_t = k_2 (q_e - q)^2 \quad (5)$$

where, k_2 is the rate constant of second order adsorption (g/mg min). For the same boundary conditions, the integrated form of eq. (5) becomes :

$$t/q = 1/k_2 q_e^2 + 1/q_e t \quad (6)$$

where, k_2 values was determined from the slope of the plots of t/q against t (Fig. 4). The values of the parameters and correlation coefficients are also presented in Table 5. The correlation coefficients of all examined data were found very high ($R^2 > 0.99$). This shows that the model can be applied for the entire adsorption process and confirms that the sorption of dye onto activated carbon follows the pseudo-second order kinetic model.

Calculation of thermodynamic parameters : The equilibrium constant K was calculated¹⁹ with the help of data from Table 3 using following eq. (7),

$$K = q_e/C_e \quad (7)$$

where, q_e is amount of dye adsorbed at equilibrium (mg/g) and C_e is the amount remaining in solution at equilibrium (mg/L). The value of Gibbs free energy for the adsorption at different temperature using following eq. (8),

(8),

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K \quad (8)$$

where, ΔG° is standard Gibbs free energy change, R is the universal gas constant and T is absolute temperature (K). The standard free energy change is also related to standard enthalpy change (ΔH°) and the standard entropy change (ΔS°) by eq. (9),

$$\Delta G^\circ = \Delta H^\circ - T\Delta S^\circ \quad (9)$$

From eqs. (8) and (9), we obtained :

$$\ln K = -\Delta H^\circ/RT + \Delta S^\circ/R \quad (10)$$

Hence, from the slope and intercept of plot $\ln K$ vs $1/T$, the value of ΔH° and ΔS° were obtained. Values of all the thermodynamic parameters are given in Table 6.

Table 6. Thermodynamic parameters for the adsorption of BG dye by activated carbon

Temp. (T) (K)	Standard Gibbs free energy change (ΔG°) (kJ/mol)	Standard enthalpy change (ΔH°) (kJ/mol)	Standard entropy change (ΔS°) (kJ/mol K)
303	-3003.82		
313	-2502.61	-2433.78	70.16
323	-1600.51		

Conclusions :

An activated carbon prepared from coconut fiber has been used as an adsorbent for the removal of dye from solution. Adsorption was influenced by various parameters such as initial dye concentration, adsorbent dose, temperature and pH. The maximum uptake of dye occurred at pH 7.0. Adsorption was increased with increasing dose of adsorbent and decreased with increasing initial dye concentration. Kinetic and isothermal studies revealed that activated carbon can be effectively employed for the adsorption of dye. Adsorption follows both type of isotherm that is Langmuir and Freundlich but Langmuir best fitted than Freundlich. Adsorption was best fitted by the pseudo-second order model.

Experimental

Materials : The reagent grade Brilliant Green dye (B.D.H.), H_2SO_4 (Merck) were used. The coconut fiber was collected from local market of Allahabad, Uttar Pradesh, India.

Fig. 4. Pseudo-second order adsorption kinetic data for dye onto activated carbon.

Instruments : pH meter (Century-CP 901), orbital shaker (Shivam, ISO 900/2000), UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Systronics 104) were used in this work.

Preparation of activated carbon : Coconut fiber was treated with 500 mL of 1 M H₂SO₄. The material was repeatedly washed with distilled water and heated in oven at 150 °C for 12 h and then powdered. The powder was sieved through 120 mesh and was used for all the experiments. The activated carbon was characterized for physico-chemical properties like pH (6.4), surface area²⁰ (14 m² g⁻¹), moisture²¹ (10%), ion exchange capacity²² (0.87 meq g⁻¹).

Batch experiments : In the present study adsorption was carried out by agitating 100 mL aqueous solution of the dyes of desired concentration (Brilliant Green) at different concentrations, temperatures, pH and adsorbent dose in different conical flasks in a orbital shaker at 125 rpm. The pH of solution was adjusted by adding HCl or NaOH. After defined time intervals, samples were withdrawn from the shaker, centrifuged and the supernatant solution of Brilliant Green dye were analysed by spectrophotometer at 625 nm. Blank samples were also run under similar conditions of concentration.

References

1. S. Rajeshwari, S. Sivakumar, P. Senthilkumar and V. Subburam, *Bioresource Technology*, 2001, **80**, 233.
2. C. K. Lee, K. S. Low and P. Gan, *Environmental Technology*, 1999, **20**, 99.
3. S. Pappic, N. Koprivanac and A. Metes, *Environmental Technology*, 2000, **21**, 97.
4. G. McKay, M. Elgundi and M. M. Nassar, *Water Research*, 1988, **22**, 1527.
5. Y. Anjaneyulu and V. Himabindu, *J. Env. and Pollut.*, 2001, **8**, 117.
6. S. Rajeshwari, C. Namasivayam and K. Kadirvelu, *Waste Mgt.*, 2001, **21**, 105.
7. C. Namasivayam and K. Kadirvelu, *Bioresource Technology*, 1994, **48**, 79.
8. S. P. Raghuvanshi, A. K. Raghav, R. Singh and A. Chandra, "Investigation of Sawdust as Adsorbent for the Removal of Methylene Blue Dye in Aqueous Solutions", in 'Proceedings of International Conference for Water and Wastewater – Perspectives in Developing Countries (WAPDEC)', International Water Association, UK, 2002, 1053.
9. N. Deo and M. Ali, *Indian J. Envt. Prot.*, 1993, **13**, 496.
10. C. Namasivayam and K. Kadirvelu, *Bioresource Technology*, 1997, **62**, 123.
11. R. Singh, M.Tech Thesis, Department of Environmental Sciences and Engineering, Guru Jambheshwar University, Hisar, Haryana, India, 2001.
12. S. P. Raghuvanshi, M.Tech Thesis, Department of Environmental Sciences and Engineering, Guru Jambheshwar University, Hisar, Haryana, India, 2001.
13. I. S. Singh, PhD Thesis, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi, India, 1974.
14. I. Langmuir, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, **38**, 2221.
15. H. M. F. Freundlich, U ber die adsorption in lo "sungen", *Zeist chrift fur Physikalische Chemie*, 1906, **57**, 385.
16. M. H. Kalavathy, T. Karthikeyan, S. Rajgopal and L. R. Miranda, *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science*, 2005, **292**, 354.
17. S. Lagergren, Zur theorie der sogenannten adsorption geloster stoffe kungliga svenska vetenskapsakademiens, *Handlingar*, 1898, **24**, 1.
18. Y. S. Ho, G. McKay, D. A. J. Wase and C. F. Foster, *Adsorp. Sci. Technol.*, 2000, **18**, 639.
19. J. C. Igwe and A. A. Abia, *Global Journal of Environmental Research*, 2007, **1**, 22.
20. H. L. S. Tandon (ed.), "Methods of Analysis of Solids, Plants, Waters and Fertilizers", Fertilizer Development and Consultation Organization, New Delhi, 1993.
21. G. H. Jeffery, J. Basset, J. Mendham and R. C. Deny, "Vogel's Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 5th ed., ELBS Publication, London, 1989.
22. R. P. Singh, Y. Singh, N. Gupta, A. Gautam, A. Singh, R. Suman and R. R. Kulshrestha, "Removal of Cr^{VI} from Wastewater using A.C., Fly Ash and Baggase", 'Proc, 10th National Symposium on Environment', June 2001, 143.